

W6BM_README.pdf

Equipment used for WWV-5 frequency measurement:

75 meter open-wire fed antenna with tuner, E-W orientation

Hammarlund SP-600 JX-17 diversity receiver “red knobs”

Receiver oscillators replaced by a stack of synthesizers disciplined by a Thunderbolt GPS

5455 kHz LO

Second-conversion oscillator, 3500 kHz, used on dual-conversion bands

456 kHz BFO

455 kHz time-base reference for a dual-trace oscilloscope

The frequencies are selected so there are two frequency difference mixes, so an increase of the received signal frequency produces an increase of the 1 kHz beat note frequency.

This setup is used for the ARRL and K5CM FMTs.

Linux 14.04 LTS operating system supporting fldigi on a Dell laptop computer.

Measurement from about 15:30 PDT 30 September to about 18:30 PDT 1 October 2019

Actual UTC times in file

Signal probably a mixture of WWV and WWVH.

Maidenhead location: CM87uv

Lat / Long: 37.897 / -122.268

csv file name: W6BM_CM87uv_5_MHz.csv

I also include the file W6BM_2017_Eclipse.pdf, describing my measurements of WWVB-60 during the 2017 solar eclipse, including an interesting exchange with WWV engineer Matt Deutch. This note is on the CHRS web site, along with many others by the author.

Please e-mail summary of experiment to john@w6bm.com

Author: John Staples, Ph.D. Nuclear Physics, W6BM, Extra Class and First Phone, both 1958.

Summary data plot, starting at 3:30 PDT (15:30), and ending 27 hours later, bracketing 0000 to 2400 UTC, showing frequency variation vs. West Coast clock time. Midnight is at 12 hours. Noon next day at 24 hours.